

early May. Individual plant selection was based on maturity, panicle length, grains per panicle, grain fertility, and grain acceptability (Table 1). The bulk population materials were as early as local cultivars. Some of them showed better seed fertility and grain numbers per panicle than local cultivars. Duration was about 90 d. The most promising materials are japonica/japonica crosses — Moroberekan/IRAT177 and ITA235/ Palawan. Lack of rain (108 mm) during Aug 1986 affected the reproductive and maturing stages.

Selected plants were sown 3 Oct 1986 to test cold tolerance at the vegetative stage. The transplanted crop was

Table 2. Cold tolerance of selected advanced lines of rainfed upland crosses. Malda, India, 1986-87.

Designation	Cross	Varietal group	Lines tested (no.)	Survival (%)	Average cold score (0-9 scale)	Range of cold tolerance
IR47687-10	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	3	12.5	7.0	7-7
IR47698-32	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	1	87.5	4.0	3-5
IR47688-78	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	6	45.8	7.0	5-9
IR47697-2	ITA235/IR9669 sel.	VI/I	6	62.5	5.8	3-9
IR47699-22	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	3	12.5	6.0	4-9
IR47699-28	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	2	56.3	5.5	5-6
IR47701-20	ITA235/UPLRi-7	VI/I	3	43.8	8.0	7-9
IR47705-6	Moroberekan/Palawan	VI/VI	8	64.5	6.7	5-9
IR47721-21	IRAT177/H.T. Boewani	VI/I	6	52.5	4.7	1-9
IR47724-14	Moroberekan/IRAT177	VI/VI	3	33.8	6.6	6-7
IR47730-4	IRAT112/Apura	VI/I	5	12.5	6.5	6-7
Soni	Local check			25.0	9.0	8-9
Dular	Local check			12.5	9.0	9-9

screened 3 Jan 1987. Average minimum temperatures were 18 °C in Nov and

13 °C in Dec. Table 2 shows crosses promising for survival percentage. □

Japonica and indica differences in large vascular bundles in culm

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We studied the number of large vascular bundles in the first internode from the

top (NLVBFI) and the number of primary branches of panicle (NPBP) at heading, in 45 indica (hsien) and japonica (keng) type varieties during 1981-82. NLVBFI was 20.9 ± 6.3 for indica type and 10.1 ± 1.9 for japonica type (see table). NPBP showed almost no differences between the two types. The ratio for NLVBFI/NPBP for 10 indicas averaged 1.97 and ranged from

1.64 to 2.27. The ratio for 10 japonicas averaged 1.13 and ranged from 1.02 to 1.19.

It seems that the ratio can be considered a new character to distinguish the two types. The difference in NLVBFI between the two types may relate to evolution and to nutrient transport. □

NLVBFI and NPBP^a in selected indica and japonica varieties. Hunan, China.

	NLVBFI		NPBP		A/B
	Average (A)	CV (%)	Average (B)	CV (%)	
<i>Indica</i>					
Guang-lu-ai 4	14.6	8.7	7.2	12.8	2.08
Yu-chi 231-8	15.5	8.7	8.0	8.8	1.94
Xiang-ai-zhao 9	18.1	6.1	8.2	15.0	2.21
Ke-zhen 145	27.5	9.1	16.0	5.6	1.69
Wei-you 6	24.1	16.0	12.0	5.6	2.01
Zhen-zhu-ai	22.7	13.6	11.4	9.4	1.99
Qui-chao 2	22.9	9.5	11.6	7.3	1.97
Qiang-yan 1811	18.7	8.7	9.6	11.1	1.95
Mi-yan 23	23.2	10.7	10.2	11.1	2.27
IR26	18.7	14.9	11.2	5.6	1.64
<i>Japonica</i>					
Tian-jin-yong	12.0	9.6	10.8	8.5	1.11
Long-hu 6	11.7	7.0	10.2	12.0	1.14
58 fu-nuo	8.3	9.9	7.0	19.0	1.18
177 fu-lei	10.7	15.7	10.5	14.3	1.02
6107	11.0	14.8	10.3	17.8	1.07
78-14	9.5	12.9	8.0	13.4	1.19
4001	10.3	20.9	9.2	25.2	1.12
Hai203	9.5	8.8	8.0	11.8	1.19
Yi-chang 105	11.6	10.8	10.6	15.4	1.09

^aMeans of 10 plants, including 5 main culms and 5 tillers. NLVBFI = large vascular bundles in first internode, NPBP = primary branches of panicle.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Correlation between rice grain and straw protein content and yield

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BR3 rice was grown at the Bangladesh Agricultural University Farm, Mymensingh, May-Oct 1982 with 4 treatments of ZnO (0, 2, 5, and 8 kg Zn/ha) and gypsum (0, 20,30, and 40

kg S/ ha). Normal cultural operations were done.

The experiment was in randomized block design with four replications. Seedlings (25 d old) were transplanted 22 May at 25- × 15-cm spacing and harvested at 134 d.

Rough grain and straw yields were recorded. Samples of rough grain and straw were analyzed for protein content by the improved Kjeldahl method (N × 6.25).

There was a significant positive correlation between grain protein content and yield ($r = 0.84^{**}$) and straw protein content and yield ($r = 0.79^{**}$) (Fig. 1, 2). □

1. Correlation between rice grain yield and protein content. Chittagong, Bangladesh.

2. Correlation between rice straw yield and protein content. Chittagong, Bangladesh.

Disease resistance

Tungro (RTV) transmission and mode of green leafhopper (GLH) feeding

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We studied the relationship between feeding behavior of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and transmission of RTV-associated viruses in seedlings of nine rice cultivars. Newly emerged adults from a GLH colony reared on rice

Cultivar	GLH reaction	GLH (no.) that transmitted				GLH (no.) feeders on		
		5	10	15	20	Phloem + Phloem	xylem	Xylem
ASD 7	R	RTBV + RTSV	1	0	0	0	0	1
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	1	7
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	10	0	0	0	0	11
Gam Pai 30-12-15	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	4	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	6	8
Palasithari 601	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	4	1
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	5	10
Utri Rajapan	S	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	2	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	16	0
Habiganj DW8	S	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	3	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	17	0
TKM6	MR to MS	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	2	2
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	15	0	0	0	3	13
ARC11554	R	RTBV + RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RTBV	5	0	0	0	0	2
		RTSV	5	0	0	0	0	2
		None	15	0	0	0	0	16
IR22	S	RTBV + RTSV	10	0	0	0	12	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	7	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	5	0	0	0	1	0
TN1	S	RTBV + RTSV	10	0	0	0	8	0
		RTBV	10	0	0	0	9	0
		RTSV	0	0	0	0	0	0
		None	5	0	0	0	3	0

1. Transmission of RTBV or RTSV or both by GLH and insect mode during inoculation access feeding on 9 selected rice cultivars. IRRI, 1987.